

Combinatorial Techniques for Binomial Expansions with Multiples of 2

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Abstract: This paper present the results of binomial expansions which are equal to exponents of two. These combinatorial and binomial results are useful for researchers who are working in computing, science, engineering, and management.

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1. Introduction

Combinatorial and computing techniques [1-9] use the binomial coefficients, combinatorial expansions, factorials, and integers for the applications in science, computing, communication and cybersecurity [1-3]. The traditional coefficient and optimized binomial coefficient and its relationships are given below. The optimized binomial coefficients [4-10] are used for the development of the binomial expansions and series constituted on the multiple summations of geometric series [11-17].

Let $N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots, \}$ be the set of natural numbers including zero element.

Tradional binomial coefficient: $nC_r = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!}$, where $n, r \in N$.

Optimized binomial coefficient: $V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)(r+3)\dots(r+n)}{n!}$, ($n \geq 1, r \geq 0$ & $n, r \in N$).

The otimized binomial coefficient is $V_x^y = V_y^x$. Let $z = x + y$, where $x, y, z \in N$.

The traditonal binomial coefficient $zC_x = zC_y = \frac{z!}{x!(z-y)!} = \frac{(x+y)!}{x!y!}$.

Here, $V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = 1$ & $V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1$.

2. Binomial Expansion

(1) if n is a possitve odd integer, then $V_0^n + V_1^{n-1} + V_2^{n-2} + V_3^{n-3} + \dots + V_{\frac{n-1}{2}}^{\frac{n+1}{2}} = 2^{n-1}$.

(2) if n is a possitve even integer, then $V_0^n + V_1^{n-1} + V_2^{n-2} + V_3^{n-3} + \dots + \frac{1}{2}V_{\frac{n}{2}}^{\frac{n}{2}} = 2^{n-1}$.

(3) $\sum_{i=0}^0 V_i^{0-i} + \sum_{i=0}^1 V_i^{1-i} + \sum_{i=0}^2 V_i^{2-i} + \sum_{i=0}^3 V_i^{3-i} + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = \sum_{i=0}^n 2^i$,

where $V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = 1$ & $V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1$.

$$(4) \sum_{i=1}^1 i \times V_i^{1-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 i \times V_i^{2-i} + \sum_{i=1}^3 i \times V_i^{3-i} + \dots + \sum_{i=1}^n i \times V_i^{n-i} = \sum_{i=1}^n i \times 2^{i-1}.$$

The binomial expansions (1), (2) & (3) are proved using the result $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n$,

and the binomial expansion (4) is proved using the result $\sum_{i=0}^n i \times V_i^{n-i} = n2^{n-1}$.

Proof for the binomial expansions (1) & (2):

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n \Rightarrow V_0^n + V_1^{n-1} + V_2^{n-2} + V_3^{n-3} + \dots + V_{n-3}^3 + V_{n-2}^2 + V_{n-1}^1 + V_n^0 = 2^n.$$

We can rearrange this binomial series as follows.

If n is a positive odd integer, the binomial series is given below:

$$V_0^n + V_1^{n-1} + V_2^{n-2} + \dots + V_{\frac{n-1}{2}}^{\frac{n+1}{2}} + V_{\frac{n+1}{2}}^{\frac{n-1}{2}} + \dots + V_{n-2}^2 + V_{n-1}^1 + V_n^0 = 2^n.$$

In this binomial series, the number of terms is even. So, we can write the series as follows:

$$2(V_0^n + V_1^{n-1} + V_2^{n-2} + \dots + V_{\frac{n-1}{2}}^{\frac{n+1}{2}}) = 2^n \quad (\because V_r^n = V_n^r \text{ \& } V_r^0 = V_0^n = 1), \text{ that is,}$$

$$V_0^n + V_1^{n-1} + V_2^{n-2} + \dots + V_{\frac{n-1}{2}}^{\frac{n+1}{2}} = 2^{n-1}. \text{ Hence, the binomial expansion (1) is proved.}$$

If n is a positive even integer, the binomial series is given below:

$$V_0^n + V_1^{n-1} + V_2^{n-2} + \dots + V_{\frac{n-2}{2}}^{\frac{n+2}{2}} + V_{\frac{n}{2}}^2 + V_{\frac{n+2}{2}}^{\frac{n-2}{2}} + \dots + V_{n-2}^2 + V_{n-1}^1 + V_n^0 = 2^n.$$

Next, the number of terms is odd in even integer series. So, we can write the series as follows:

$$2(V_0^n + V_1^{n-1} + V_2^{n-2} + \dots + V_{\frac{n-2}{2}}^{\frac{n+2}{2}} + \frac{1}{2} V_{\frac{n}{2}}^2) = 2^n \quad (\because V_r^n = V_n^r \text{ \& } V_r^0 = V_0^n = 1), \text{ that is,}$$

$$V_0^n + V_1^{n-1} + V_2^{n-2} + \dots + V_{\frac{n-2}{2}}^{\frac{n+2}{2}} + \frac{1}{2} V_{\frac{n}{2}}^2 = 2^{n-1}. \text{ Hence, the binomial series (2) is proved.}$$

For examples,

$$\text{If } n = 11, V_0^{11} + V_1^{10} + V_2^9 + V_3^8 + V_4^7 + V_5^6 = 2^{11-1} = 2^{10}.$$

$$\text{If } n = 12, V_0^{12} + V_1^{11} + V_2^{10} + V_3^9 + V_4^8 + V_5^7 + \frac{1}{2} V_6^6 = 2^{12-1} = 2^{11}.$$

Proof for the binomial series (3): $V_0^0 = 1 \Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^0 V_i^{0-i} = 2^0$; $\sum_{i=0}^1 V_i^{i-i} = V_0^1 + V_1^0 = 2^1$;

$$\sum_{i=0}^2 V_i^{i-i} = V_0^2 + V_1^1 + V_2^0 = 2^2$$
; $\sum_{i=0}^3 V_i^{i-i} = V_0^3 + V_1^2 + V_2^1 + V_3^0 = 2^3.$

Similarly, we can continue this process upto n such that $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n$.

When making the summation on both sides, we get

$$\sum_{i=0}^0 V_i^{0-i} + \sum_{i=0}^1 V_i^{1-i} + \sum_{i=0}^2 V_i^{2-i} + \sum_{i=0}^3 V_i^{3-i} + \dots + \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = \sum_{i=0}^n 2^i. \text{ Hence, it is proved.}$$

Proof for the binomial expansion (4): $\sum_{i=1}^1 i \times V_i^{i-1} = 1 \times V_1^0 = 1 \times 2^{1-1} = 1 \times 2^0$;

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 i \times V_i^{2-1} = 1 \times V_1^1 + 2 \times V_2^0 = 4 = 2 \times 2^1; \sum_{i=1}^3 i \times V_i^{3-1} = 3 \times 2^2.$$

Similarly, we can continue this process upto n such that $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = n \times 2^{n-1}$.

When making the summation on both sides, we get

$$\sum_{i=1}^1 i \times V_i^{1-i} + \sum_{i=1}^2 i \times V_i^{2-i} + \sum_{i=1}^3 i \times V_i^{3-i} + \dots + \sum_{i=1}^n i \times V_i^{n-i} = \sum_{i=1}^n i \times 2^{i-1}.$$

Hence, the binomial expansion (4) is proved.

3. Conclusion

This article has provided the results of binomial expansions which are equal to multiples and exponents of 2. These combinatorial and computing results are useful for researchers who are working in science, engineering, management, and medicine [16, 17].

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